

Aluminum solubility in bridgmanite up to 3000 K at the top lower mantle

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<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.gsf.2020.04.009>

Accepted manuscript

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2 **mantle**

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9

10 **Abstract**

11 The temperature dependence of the Al₂O₃ solubility in bridgmanite has been
12 determined in the system MgSiO₃–Al₂O₃ at temperatures of 2750–3000 K under a
13 constant pressure of 27 GPa using a multi-anvil apparatus. Bridgmanite becomes more
14 aluminous with increasing temperatures. A LiNbO₃-type phase with a pyrope
15 composition (Mg₃Al₂Si₃O₁₂) forms at 2850 K, which is regarded as to be transformed
16 from bridgmanite upon decompression. This phase contains 30 mol% Al₂O₃ at 3000 K.
17 The MgSiO₃ solubility in corundum also increases with temperatures, reaching 52 mol%
18 at 3000 K. Molar volumes of the hypothetical Al₂O₃ bridgmanite and MgSiO₃
19 corundum are constrained to be 25.95 ± 0.05 and 26.24 ± 0.06 cm³/mol, respectively,
20 and interaction parameters of non-ideality for these two phases are 5.6 ± 0.5 and 2.2 ±
21 0.5 KJ/mol, respectively. The increases in Al₂O₃ and MgSiO₃ contents, respectively, in
22 bridgmanite and corundum are caused by a larger entropy of Al₂O₃ bridgmanite plus
23 MgSiO₃ corundum than that of MgSiO₃ bridgmanite plus Al₂O₃ corundum with
24 temperature, in addition to the configuration entropy. Our study may help explain
25 dynamics of the top lower mantle and constrain pressure and temperature conditions of
26 shocked meteorites.

27

28 **Keywords:** Bridgmanite; LiNbO₃-type phase; Corundum; Temperature; Entropy;
29 Lower mantle

30

31 **1. Introduction**

32 Geochemical and petrological studies suggest that Earth's lower mantle (660–2900
33 km depth), which occupies more than 50% of Earth's volume, is the largest
34 geochemical reservoir in the Earth (e.g., Ringwood, 1975; Anderson, 1983;
35 McDonough and Sun, 1995). Bridgmanite is the most abundant phase in this region,
36 and comprises about 80% of this region in volume (Irifune, 1994). Under lower-mantle
37 conditions, bridgmanite can contain 25 mol% of alumina (Al_2O_3) (Liu et al., 2016,
38 2017a), which is far beyond its contents in the pyrolite and mid-oceanic ridge
39 basalt (MORB) compositions (Green et al., 1979; Sun, 1982). Bridgmanite is thus the
40 major host phase for the Al_2O_3 in the lower mantle (Irifune, 1996; Liu et al., 2016,
41 2017a). Al_2O_3 incorporation can greatly change chemical and physical properties of
42 bridgmanite (e.g., McCammon, 1997; Xu et al., 1998; Zhang and Weidner, 1999;
43 Brodholt, 2000). Therefore, the Al_2O_3 solubility in bridgmanite is of great significance
44 for understanding the mineralogy of the lower mantle.

45 The Al_2O_3 solubility in bridgmanite has been studied in the system $\text{MgSiO}_3\text{--Al}_2\text{O}_3$
46 by several workers (Irifune et al., 1996; Kubo and Akaogi, 2000; Hirose et al., 2001;
47 Akaogi et al., 2002). Liu et al. (2017a, 2017b) recently demonstrated that the Al_2O_3
48 solubility in bridgmanite has both positive pressure and temperature dependences at
49 pressures of 27–52 GPa and temperatures of 1700–2500 K. They also predicted that a
50 LiNbO_3 -structured phase (LN) with a pyrope ($\text{Mg}_3\text{Al}_2\text{Si}_3\text{O}_{12}$) composition should form
51 at 2750–2800 K under 27 GPa upon decompression. LN has been regarded as a
52 metastable phase formed from high-pressure stable bridgmanite by a diffusionless
53 transformation upon decompression (e.g., Ross et al., 1989; Liu et al., 2006). The
54 formation of LN can help understand the complicated crystal chemistry of bridgmanite
55 and constrains shock conditions of meteorites (Ishii et al., 2017; Liu et al., 2019).
56 However, the temperature dependence of Al_2O_3 solubility in bridgmanite is still poorly
57 understood because the data obtained by our recent (Liu et al., 2017b) and earlier
58 (Irifune et al., 1996; Kubo and Akaogi, 2000; Hirose et al., 2001; Akaogi et al., 2002)
59 studies did not agree well. Furthermore, the chemistry of Al_2O_3 component in
60 bridgmanite remains unknown at temperatures higher than 2500 K. At higher

61 temperatures, oxygen vacancies in the form of an $\text{MgAlO}_{2.5}$ component should increase,
62 and might thereby decrease the Al_2O_3 component (Brodholt, 2000; Navrotsky et al.,
63 2003; Liu et al., 2019a, 2019b), which should decrease ferropericlasite in the lower
64 mantle. Temperatures in hot plumes from the lower mantle should be significantly
65 higher by 500–1000 K than the surrounding mantle (e.g., Farnetani, 1997).
66 Consequently, temperature effects are vital to constrain dynamics of the lower mantle.
67 Nevertheless, our limited knowledge about the Al_2O_3 solubility in bridgmanite at very
68 high temperatures prevents our understandings mantle dynamics.

69 Here, we investigated the Al_2O_3 solubility in bridgmanite at temperatures up to 3000
70 K and a constant pressure of 27 GPa in a multi-anvil press. This pressure can prevent
71 the formation of majoritic garnet. Based on our new results, we have determined the
72 temperature dependence of the Al_2O_3 solubility in bridgmanite together with the
73 MgSiO_3 solubility in corundum, estimated thermoelastic parameters of bridgmanite and
74 corundum, and discussed their implications for dynamics of the lower mantle.

75

76 **2. Experimental methods**

77 $\text{En}_{75}\text{Cor}_{25}$ ($\text{Mg}_3\text{Al}_2\text{Si}_3\text{O}_{12}$, En: MgSiO_3 , Cor: Al_2O_3 ; the number represents mol%)
78 and $\text{En}_{65}\text{Cor}_{35}$ glasses are used as starting materials. Detailed chemical composition of
79 the $\text{En}_{75}\text{Cor}_{25}$ glass was reported in Liu et al. (2016), and that of the $\text{En}_{65}\text{Cor}_{35}$ glass
80 was confirmed in the present study to have the intended composition using an electron
81 probe microanalyzer. Starting materials were put into rhenium (Re) capsules made of
82 25 μm thick foils, and then heated at 500 K for half an hour to purge water. The capsules
83 with starting materials were finally put into cell assemblies. Quench experiments at a
84 constant pressure of 27 GPa and temperatures of 2700–3000 K were performed using a
85 Cr_2O_3 -doped MgO (OMCR, Mino Ceramic Co., LTD.) octahedra with a 7-mm edge
86 length and LaCrO_3 sleeves for heating in combination with tungsten carbide cubes with
87 3 mm truncated edge lengths in a multi-anvil apparatus (IRIS-15) with a press load of
88 15 MN at the Bayerisches Geoinstitut, University of Bayreuth (Ishii et al., 2016).
89 Temperature was monitored with a W_{97}Re_3 - $\text{W}_{75}\text{Re}_{25}$ thermocouple placed adjacent to
90 the Re capsule. The adapted cell assembly can be referred to Fig. 1. The pressure at

91 high temperatures was calibrated by the decomposition of pyrope into aluminous
92 bridgmanite and corundum and the Al_2O_3 solubility in bridgmanite at various
93 temperatures (Liu et al., 2017b). Pressure uncertainties of these quench experiments are
94 ± 1 GPa.

95 Phases in quench runs were identified using a micro-focused X-ray diffractometer
96 (XRD, Bruker, D8 DISCOVER) equipped with a Co tube operated at 40 kV and 500
97 μA . X-ray beams were focused to 50 μm in diameter using an IFG polycapillary X-ray
98 mini-lens. The XRD profile of each sample was collected for three hours. Textural
99 observation was performed using a LEO1530 scanning electron microscope (SEM)
100 operating at an acceleration voltage of 15 kV and a beam current of 10 nA. Chemical
101 compositions of each phase present in the quench runs were determined using a JEOL
102 JXA-8200 electron probe microanalyzer (EPMA) operating at acceleration voltages of
103 15 kV and a beam current of 5 nA with standards of enstatite for Mg and Si, and
104 corundum for Al.

105

106 **3. Results**

107 Experimental conditions and phases present in the recovered samples are listed in
108 Table 1.

109 Fig. 1a shows cross section of the cell assembly, and Fig. 1b plots the generated
110 temperature as a function of the power supplied by the LaCrO_3 heater at 27 GPa. It is
111 clearly seen that the temperature can successfully read 2399 °C. Above this temperature,
112 we cannot read temperature because it exceeded the limit of temperature display of the
113 thermometer. We thereby estimated the temperature from the extrapolation by a cubic
114 polynomial fitting of the temperatures below 2399 °C and heating power. In the run
115 627, the heating power reached ~ 760 W and the estimated temperature was $\sim 3000 \pm 50$
116 K.

117 Fig. 2 shows the XRD patterns of run products. Fig. 3 shows their back-scattered
118 electron (BSE) images. At 2750 K, both XRD and BSE observations exhibit that run
119 products from $\text{En}_{75}\text{Cor}_{25}$ consist of LN with trace amounts of corundum, bridgmanite,
120 and stishovite (Figs. 2a and 3a). We assume that LN is a product of back-transformation

121 of bridgmanite upon decompression based on previous results (Funamori et al., 1997;
122 Miyajima et al., 1999; Liu et al., 2016, 2017a; Ishii et al., 2017). Therefore, we refer to
123 the composition of LN as “bridgmanite composition” hereafter. The formation of large
124 amounts of LN in this bulk composition indicates that bridgmanite incorporates close
125 to 25 mol% of Al_2O_3 even at the pressure much lower than previous studies, above 40
126 GPa (Liu et al., 2017). Trace amounts of bridgmanite may be a metastable remnant from
127 the back-transition. The BSE image shows no distinguishable BSE signal intensities
128 between LN and bridgmanite, indicating identical compositions of these two phases.
129 One of these phases (bridgmanite) should therefore be metastable based on no binary
130 phase loop of these two phases. From the run at 2850 K, the run product completely
131 consists of a single LN with grain sizes larger than 10 μm . From the runs at 2850 and
132 3000 K from $\text{En}_{65}\text{Cor}_{35}$, the run product consists of a mixture of LN and corundum
133 based on XRD identifications and BSE observations (Figs. 2c, d and 3c, d).

134 One question is whether melting occurs at the highest experimental temperature of
135 3000 K (run 627). SEM observations, however, did not show any features of melting in
136 this run as follows. First, phase compositions are identical within analytical
137 uncertainties in the radial direction. Second, although particles of Re or its oxide are
138 found in the boundary of LN and corundum (Fig. 3b–d), the amounts of these particles
139 significantly increase from the center to the ends of the sample capsule. These Re
140 phases are thought to have been formed by a solid diffusion of the capsule at very high
141 temperatures (Thévenin et al., 1993). Furthermore, Kudo and Ito (1996) studied the
142 melting phase relations in this system at 25 GPa and reported that bridgmanite with 10
143 mol% Al_2O_3 melted at higher temperature than the melting temperature of the pure
144 MgSiO_3 bridgmanite, which is 2900 K. Their report suggested that the incorporation of
145 Al_2O_3 component must raise the melting temperature of bridgmanite. These
146 observations and report lead to the conclusion that melting did not occur at the
147 temperature of the run 627. Therefore, the melting temperature of bridgmanite with the
148 $\text{En}_{75}\text{Cor}_{25}$ composition should be higher than 3000 K at 27 GPa.

149 Compositional analysis by EPMA confirms that LN/bridgmanite contained 24 ± 1
150 mol% Al_2O_3 at 2750 K from the $\text{En}_{75}\text{Cor}_{25}$ starting material. The LN in the run 635

151 from this starting material contained 25.0 ± 0.2 mol% Al_2O_3 at 2850 K, which is
 152 identical to that of the starting material. From the $\text{En}_{65}\text{Cor}_{35}$ starting material in the
 153 same run, the Al_2O_3 content in LN reached 26 ± 1 mol%, while the MgSiO_3 content in
 154 corundum was 42 ± 1 mol%. In the run 627 (3000 K), the Al_2O_3 content in LN and the
 155 MgSiO_3 content in corundum were found to be 29 ± 1 and 52 ± 1 mol%, respectively.
 156 The lattice parameters of this LN ($a = b = 4.849$ (1) Å; $c = 12.712$ (10) Å; the number
 157 in the parenthesis represents the standard deviation for the last digit.) are slightly higher
 158 than obtained by Ishii et al. (2017) those ($a = b = 4.783$ (2) Å; $c = 12.680$ (11) Å). These
 159 differences can be explained by the higher Al_2O_3 content in the present study. As already
 160 mentioned, the formation of these Al-rich LN was recovered from bridgmanite
 161 synthesized at lower-mantle conditions through a diffusionless transition, in which the
 162 A (Mg) cations are substituted and BO_6 (B, Si) octahedra are distorted due to the
 163 incorporation of large amounts of Al (Liu et al., 2016, 2019; Ishii et al., 2017).

164

165 **4. Discussion**

166 **4.1. Thermodynamics of Al partitioning in bridgmanite and corundum**

167 To further understand the Al^{3+} exchange between bridgmanite and corundum, we
 168 conducted the thermodynamics calculation using the following reaction:

170 where Al_2O_3 and MgSiO_3 are the hypothetical end-member of bridgmanite (Brg) and
 171 corundum (Cor), respectively. The Gibbs free energy change of reaction (1) can be
 172 expressed as:

$$173 \quad \mu_{\text{MgSiO}_3}^{\text{Brg}} + \mu_{\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3}^{\text{Cor}} = \mu_{\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3}^{\text{Brg}} + \mu_{\text{MgSiO}_3}^{\text{Cor}} \quad (2)$$

174 where $\mu_{\text{MgSiO}_3}^{\text{Brg}}$ and $\mu_{\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3}^{\text{Brg}}$ are the chemical potentials of MgSiO_3 and Al_2O_3 in
 175 bridgmanite, respectively, and $\mu_{\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3}^{\text{Cor}}$ and $\mu_{\text{MgSiO}_3}^{\text{Cor}}$ are those of Al_2O_3 and MgSiO_3
 176 components in corundum, respectively. Chemical potentials of these components can
 177 be expressed as the following equations in the non-ideal solution model:

$$178 \quad \mu_{\text{MgSiO}_3}^{\text{Brg}} = \mu_{\text{MgSiO}_3}^{\circ\text{Brg}} + RT \ln a_{\text{MgSiO}_3}^{\text{Brg}} \quad (3)$$

179
$$\mu_{\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3}^{\text{Cor}} = \mu_{\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3}^{\circ\text{Cor}} + RT \ln a_{\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3}^{\text{Cor}} \quad (4)$$

180
$$\mu_{\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3}^{\text{Brg}} = \mu_{\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3}^{\circ\text{Brg}} + RT \ln a_{\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3}^{\text{Brg}} \quad (5)$$

181
$$\mu_{(\text{Mg}_{0.5}\text{Si}_{0.5})_2\text{O}_3}^{\text{Cor}} = \mu_{\text{MgSiO}_3}^{\circ\text{Cor}} + RT \ln a_{\text{MgSiO}_3}^{\text{Cor}} \quad (6)$$

182 where $\mu_{\text{MgSiO}_3}^{\circ\text{Brg}}$, $\mu_{\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3}^{\circ\text{Cor}}$, $\mu_{\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3}^{\circ\text{Brg}}$, and $\mu_{(\text{Mg}_{0.5}\text{Si}_{0.5})_2\text{O}_3}^{\circ\text{Cor}}$ are the standard chemical
 183 potentials of the (hypothetical) endmembers of these four components, and $a_{\text{MgSiO}_3}^{\text{Brg}}$,
 184 $a_{\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3}^{\text{Cor}}$, $a_{\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3}^{\text{Brg}}$, and $a_{\text{MgSiO}_3}^{\text{Cor}}$ are their activities. At equilibrium, the standard state
 185 Gibbs free energy change of reaction (1) can be then expressed as:

186
$$\Delta G_{R1}^0 = \mu_{\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3}^{\circ\text{Brg}} + \mu_{(\text{Mg}_{0.5}\text{Si}_{0.5})_2\text{O}_3}^{\circ\text{Cor}} - \mu_{\text{MgSiO}_3}^{\circ\text{Brg}} - \mu_{\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3}^{\circ\text{Cor}} = RT \ln a_{\text{MgSiO}_3}^{\text{Brg}} + RT \ln a_{\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3}^{\text{Cor}} -$$

 187
$$RT \ln a_{\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3}^{\text{Brg}} - RT \ln a_{\text{MgSiO}_3}^{\text{Cor}} \quad (7)$$

188 The activity coefficients for these components in bridgmanite and corundum can be
 189 expressed as:

190
$$a_{\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3}^{\text{Brg}} = (X_{\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3}^{\text{Brg}} \cdot \gamma_{\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3}^{\text{Brg}})^2 \quad (8)$$

191
$$a_{\text{MgSiO}_3}^{\text{Brg}} = (X_{\text{MgSiO}_3}^{\text{Brg}} \cdot \gamma_{\text{MgSiO}_3}^{\text{Brg}})^2 \quad (9)$$

192
$$a_{\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3}^{\text{Cor}} = (X_{\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3}^{\text{Cor}} \cdot \gamma_{\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3}^{\text{Cor}})^2 \quad (1$$

193
$$0)$$

194
$$a_{\text{MgSiO}_3}^{\text{Cor}} = (X_{\text{MgSiO}_3}^{\text{Cor}} \cdot \gamma_{\text{MgSiO}_3}^{\text{Cor}})^2 \quad (1$$

195
$$1)$$

196 By assuming the symmetric solutions for bridgmanite and corundum, their activity
 197 coefficients can be written as:

198
$$RT \ln \gamma_{\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3}^{\text{Brg}} = W_{\text{Al}}^{\text{Brg}} (1 - X_{\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3}^{\text{Brg}})^2 \quad (12)$$

199
$$RT \ln \gamma_{\text{MgSiO}_3}^{\text{Brg}} = W_{\text{Al}}^{\text{Brg}} (1 - X_{\text{MgSiO}_3}^{\text{Brg}})^2 \quad (13)$$

200
$$RT \ln \gamma_{\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3}^{\text{Cor}} = W_{\text{Al}}^{\text{Cor}} (1 - X_{\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3}^{\text{Cor}})^2 \quad (14)$$

201
$$RT \ln \gamma_{\text{MgSiO}_3}^{\text{Cor}} = W_{\text{Al}}^{\text{Cor}} (1 - X_{\text{MgSiO}_3}^{\text{Cor}})^2 \quad (15)$$

202 where $X_{\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3}^{\text{Brg}}$ and $X_{\text{MgSiO}_3}^{\text{Brg}}$ are the mole fractions of Al_2O_3 and MgSiO_3 in bridgmanite,

203 respectively, $X_{\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3}^{\text{Cor}}$ and $X_{\text{MgSiO}_3}^{\text{Cor}}$ are the mole fractions of Al_2O_3 and MgSiO_3
 204 components in the corundum, respectively, and $W_{\text{Al}}^{\text{Brg}}$ and $W_{\text{Al}}^{\text{Cor}}$ are the interaction
 205 parameters of bridgmanite and corundum of the symmetric solutions, respectively.
 206 ΔG_{R1}^0 can be expressed as:

$$207 \quad \Delta G_{\text{R1}}^0 = -2RT \ln \frac{X_{\text{MgSiO}_3}^{\text{Cor}} X_{\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3}^{\text{Brg}}}{X_{\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3}^{\text{Cor}} X_{\text{MgSiO}_3}^{\text{Brg}}} + 2W_{\text{Al}}^{\text{Cor}} (1 - 2X_{\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3}^{\text{Cor}}) + 2W_{\text{Al}}^{\text{Brg}} (2X_{\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3}^{\text{Brg}} - 1) \quad (16)$$

208 Molar volumes of bridgmanite and corundum as a function of the Al_2O_3 and
 209 MgSiO_3 contents, respectively, are summarized in Fig. 4 (D'Amour et al., 1978; Ito et
 210 al., 1978; Irifune et al., 1996; Kubo and Akaogi, 2000; Liu et al., 2016, 2017a). It is
 211 clearly seen that molar volumes of bridgmanite and corundum, respectively, increase
 212 almost linearly with increasing Al_2O_3 and MgSiO_3 contents within analytical
 213 uncertainties. A linear relation leads to the following equation for the bridgmanite
 214 volume in cm^3/mol :

$$215 \quad V_{\text{Brg}} = 24.44 + 0.0151(5) \times \chi_{\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3} \quad (17)$$

216 where $\chi_{\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3}$ represents the mole fraction of the Al_2O_3 in bridgmanite. The derived molar
 217 volume of the hypothetical Al_2O_3 bridgmanite is to be $25.95 \pm 0.05 \text{ cm}^3/\text{mol}$. Since the
 218 molar volume of corundum is $25.56 \text{ cm}^3/\text{mol}$ under ambient conditions (D'Amour et
 219 al., 1978), the volume of Al_2O_3 bridgmanite is larger than that of pure corundum.

220 The same equation for corundum produces the following equation in cm^3/mol :

$$221 \quad V_{\text{Cor}} = 25.56 + 0.0068 (6) \times \chi_{\text{MgSiO}_3} \quad (18)$$

222 where χ_{MgSiO_3} represents mole fractions of the MgSiO_3 content in corundum. It is thus
 223 found that the effect of MgSiO_3 contents on the volume of corundum is significantly
 224 smaller than that of Al_2O_3 for bridgmanite. We have derived the molar volume of the
 225 hypothetical MgSiO_3 corundum of $26.24 \pm 0.06 \text{ cm}^3/\text{mol}$. This value is very close to the
 226 volume of MgSiO_3 akimotoite, which is $26.35 \text{ cm}^3/\text{mol}$ (Horiuchi et al., 1982). Since
 227 akimotoite has an ilmenite-structure, which is a modification of the corundum structure
 228 by cation ordering, the MgSiO_3 -bearing corundum may form a continuous solid
 229 solution with akimotoite, and cation ordering may occur from a certain composition in
 230 the Al_2O_3 – MgSiO_3 system (Panero et al., 2003).

231 We derive $W_{\text{Al}}^{\text{Cor}}$ and $W_{\text{Al}}^{\text{Brg}}$ by an empirical method for the non-ideality of solid
 232 solutions due to a mismatch of the component volumes using the following formula
 233 (Davies and Navrotsky, 1983; Akaogi and Ito, 1999):

$$234 \quad W_{\text{G}} = 100.8\Delta V - 0.4 \text{ kJ/mol} \quad (19)$$

$$235 \quad \Delta V = \frac{V_{\text{A}} - V_{\text{B}}}{(V_{\text{A}} + V_{\text{B}})/2} \quad (20)$$

236 where V_{A} and V_{B} are the molar volumes of the larger and smaller components,
 237 respectively. We then obtained the $W_{\text{Al}}^{\text{Brg}}$ and $W_{\text{Al}}^{\text{Cor}}$ values of 5.6 ± 0.2 and 2.2 ± 0.2
 238 kJ/mol, respectively, from the present molar volume results and equations of (17) and
 239 (18).

240 In Fig. 5, the derived ΔG_{R1}^0 from reaction (16) changes from $106 \pm 13 \text{ kJ}\cdot\text{mol}^{-1}$ at
 241 1700 K to $75 \pm 7 \text{ kJ}\cdot\text{mol}^{-1}$ at 2300 K and to $38 \pm 4 \text{ kJ}\cdot\text{mol}^{-1}$ at 3000 K. The composition
 242 data of bridgmanite and corundum at temperatures of 1700–2500 K is from Liu et al.
 243 (2016, 2017a). By fitting the present experimental data to a linear function of $\Delta G_{\text{R1}}^0 =$
 244 $\Delta H_{\text{R1}}^0 - T\Delta S_{\text{R1}}^0$, we obtained $\Delta S_{\text{R1}}^0 = -\left(\frac{\partial \Delta G_{\text{R1}}^0}{\partial T}\right)_P = 46 \pm 3 \text{ J}/(\text{mol}\cdot\text{K})$. This fact
 245 suggests that the configuration entropy of Al_2O_3 bridgmanite and MgSiO_3 corundum
 246 increase more than MgSiO_3 bridgmanite and Al_2O_3 corundum with increasing
 247 temperatures, which is consistent with *ab initio* calculations (Panero et al., 2003; Jung
 248 et al., 2010). It further means that heat capacities of two former components are larger
 249 than the latter components.

250 Fig. 6 illustrates the solubility of Al_2O_3 in bridgmanite and that of MgSiO_3 in
 251 corundum, respectively, as function of temperature up to 3000 K at 27 GPa in the
 252 present and previous studies (Irifune et al., 1996; Kubo and Akaogi, 2000; Akaogi et
 253 al., 2002; Liu et al., 2016, 2017a). In the present study, the Al_2O_3 solubility in
 254 bridgmanite apparently increases from 24 ± 1 to $29 \pm 1 \text{ mol}\%$ with increasing
 255 temperature from 2750 to 3000 K. At 2850 K, bridgmanite contains 25 mol% Al_2O_3 ,
 256 and thereby transforms into LN upon decompression. At 3000 K, we found that
 257 corundum incorporates the MgSiO_3 component as much as $52 \pm 1 \text{ mol}\%$, which is
 258 significantly higher than previous studies (Irifune et al., 1996; Kubo and Akaogi, 2000;
 259 Akaogi et al., 2002; Liu et al., 2016, 2017a). Dashed lines are the thermodynamic

260 calculations using the following equation:

$$\begin{aligned} 261 \quad \Delta G_{R1}(P, T, X) = & \Delta H_T^0 - T\Delta S_T^0 + \int_1^P \Delta V_{P,T} + 2RT \ln \frac{X_{\text{MgSiO}_3}^{\text{Cor}} X_{\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3}^{\text{Brg}}}{X_{\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3}^{\text{Cor}} X_{\text{MgSiO}_3}^{\text{Brg}}} - 2W_{\text{Al}}^{\text{Cor}} (1 - 2X_{\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3}^{\text{Cor}}) - \\ 262 \quad & 2W_{\text{Al}}^{\text{Brg}} (2X_{\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3}^{\text{Brg}} - 1) \end{aligned} \quad (21)$$

263 where ΔH_T^0 is the enthalpy; ΔS_T^0 is the configuration entropy; T is temperature; P is
264 the pressure; $\Delta V_{P,T}$ is the molar volume at high pressure and high temperature.
265 Thermoelastic parameters of bridgmanite and corundum can be found in the present
266 study for molar volume and entropy, and other parameters from Akaogi and Ito (1999)
267 and Liu et al. (2019b). Our thermodynamics calculations show almost consistent results
268 for the experimental data of bridgmanite. However, there exists some difference
269 between our calculation and experimental data for corundum at temperature above 2400
270 K. This may be caused by poorly constrained thermoelastic parameters and large
271 uncertainties of the interaction parameter for the Al_2O_3 corundum– MgSiO_3 akimotoite,
272 which needs further studies.

273 4.2. Implications

274 It is clearly found that the Al_2O_3 solubility in bridgmanite significantly increases
275 with increasing temperatures. Bridgmanite can contain the Al_2O_3 content up to 30 mol%
276 at 3000 K even at a relatively low pressure of 27 GPa. This value is far beyond it in
277 MORB compositions. From subducted basaltic slabs to the surrounding ambient lower
278 mantle, and then to upwelling of hot plumes at the top region of the lower mantle,
279 bridgmanite would become more aluminous due to increasing temperatures in this order,
280 if the hot plumes have a higher Al_2O_3 content than slabs and ambient lower mantle. If
281 the plume at the top region of the lower mantle is dominated by bridgmanite,
282 bridgmanite with a higher Al_2O_3 content would become denser. Therefore, it may play
283 the role of a barrier for the high temperature plumes upwelling from the lower mantle.

284 The LN can be used an indicator for constraining pressure and temperature
285 conditions of shocked meteorites (e.g., Sharp et al. 1997; Ishii et al, 2017). The present
286 study shows a clear temperature dependence of the Al_2O_3 content in LN at the top lower
287 mantle. Therefore, the presence of LN with aluminous enstatite compositions could be
288 used to constrain the formation conditions of shocked meteorites. It is emphasized that,

289 however, the presence of LN or bridgmanite with a garnet composition does not directly
290 mean that the shock pressure was above 40 GPa (Ishii et al, 2017; Liu et al., 2019c). If
291 the temperature had been higher than 2000 K, the shock pressure should be lower than
292 40 GPa, and it can be 27 GPa if the temperature were above 2800 K.

293

294 **5. Conclusions**

295 Phase relations in the system $\text{MgSiO}_3\text{--Al}_2\text{O}_3$ have been studied at temperatures of
296 2750–3000 K under a constant pressure of 27 GPa in a multi-anvil press. It is found
297 that both the Al_2O_3 and MgSiO_3 contents, respectively, in bridgmanite and corundum
298 have a positive temperature dependence. Bridgmanite with the Al_2O_3 content higher
299 than 25 mol% transforms into LN upon decompression due to the incorporation of large
300 amounts of Al. Bridgmanite and corundum, respectively, contain the Al_2O_3 and MgSiO_3
301 contents up to 30 and 52 mol.% at a temperature of 3000 K. We constrained the partial
302 molar volumes and interaction parameters of the hypothetical end-members of Al_2O_3
303 bridgmanite and MgSiO_3 corundum. The increase in Al_2O_3 and MgSiO_3 contents,
304 respectively, in bridgmanite and corundum with temperature is enhanced by their
305 positive entropy in addition to the configuration entropy. Temperature dependence of
306 the Al_2O_3 content in bridgmanite would help understand the dynamics of the lower
307 mantle and constrain the pressure and temperature conditions for shocked meteorites.

308

309 **Acknowledgments**

310 We thank E. Posner, D. Krauße, R. Njul, H. Fischer, and S. Übelhack for their assistance
311 with sample and high-pressure assembly preparation. The manuscript is greatly
312 improved by the constructive comments of Shatskiy Anton and one anonymous
313 reviewers and the handing editor. Z. L. was financially supported by the Bayerisches
314 Geoinstitut Visitor's Program and the Fundamental Research Funds for the Central
315 Universities of Ministry of Education of China (Grant No. 45119031C037). This
316 project has received funding from the European Research Council (ERC) under the
317 European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme (Proposal No.
318 787 527) It is also supported by research grants to T. K. (BMBF: 05K13WC2,

319 05K16WC2; DFG: KA3434/3-1, KA3434/7-1, KA3434/8-1, KA3434/9-1) and Z. L.
320 (the National Science Foundation of China Grant No. 41902034).

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Figures caption

Figure 1. (a) Cross section of the cell assembly. (b) Generated temperature as a function of the heating powder. The inner picture is the BSE image of the recovered assembly of the run IRIS624.

Figure 2. XRD profiles of the run products. The number in parenthesis represents the miller indices of the first appearing phase. Question marks represent the unknown peaks. Abbreviations: Brg, bridgmanite; Cor, corundum; LN, LiNbO₃-type phase; Sti,

447 stishovite; Re, rhenium.

448 **Figure 3.** BSE images of run products. Abbreviations: Brg, bridgmanite; Cor,
449 corundum; LN, the LiNbO₃-type phase; Sti, stishovite; Re, rhenium.

450 **Figure 4.** Molar volume of bridgmanite and corundum in the system MgSiO₃–Al₂O₃ in
451 previous studies.

452 **Figure 5.** Gibbs free energy of reaction (1) as a function of temperature. The data at
453 temperatures of 1700–2500 K are from Liu et al. (2016, 2017a).

454 **Figure 6.** The Al₂O₃ and MgSiO₃ contents, respectively, in bridgmanite and corundum
455 as a function of temperature. Dashed lines are thermodynamics calculation results.